

A STUDY OF ASSET AND LIABILITY MANAGEMENT WITH REFERENCE TO DYTECH ENGINEERING (INDIA) PVT.LTD

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Abstract:

Asset liability management is concerned with strategic balance sheet management involving risks caused by changes in interest rates, exchanges rate, credit risks & the liquidity position of industry. Asset liability management is about management of net interest margin to ensure that its level & riskiness are compatibles with risk/return objectives of the industry. It is more than just managing individual asset & liabilities. In addition, asset liability management requires an understanding of the market is in which the industry operates. Asset liability management is required to match asset liabilities and minimize liquidity as well as market risk. An effective asset liability management technique aims to manage the volume mix, maturity, rate, sensitivity, quality & liquidity of assets & liabilities as a whole so as to attain a predetermined acceptable risk/ reward ration.

Keywords: Asset, Liability, life insurance, Asset liability management, financial management

Introduction

Business involves the identifying, measuring, accepting and managing the risk: the heart of financial management is the risk management. One of the most important risk management function in industry is asset liability management.

Asset liability management is concerned with strategic balance sheet management involving risk caused by changes in interest rate, exchange rate, credit risk and the liquidity position of industry. With profit becoming a key factor, it has now become imperative for industry to move towards integrated balance sheet management where components of balance sheet and its different maturity mix will be looked at profit angle of the industry

ALM is about management of net interest margin to ensure that its level and riskiness are compatible with risk are return objective of the industry. It is more than just manger individual assets and liabilities. It is and integrated approach to industry financial management requiring simultaneous decision about types and amount of financial assets and liabilities it holds or its mix and volume. In addition, ALM requires an understanding of the market area in which the industry operates.

It 50% of the liabilities are maturing within year but only 10% of the assets are maturing within the same period. Though the financial institution has enough assets. It may become temporarily

insolvent due to a severe liquidity crisis. Thus, ALM is required to match assets & liabilities and minimize liquidity as well as market risk.

Asset-liability management (ALM) is a term whose meaning has evolved. It is used in slightly different ways in different contexts. ALM was pioneered by financial institutions, but corporations now also apply ALM techniques. Traditionally, banks and insurance companies used accrual accounting for essentially all their assets and liabilities. They would take on liabilities, such as deposits, life insurance policies or annuities. They would invest the proceeds from these liabilities in assets such as loans, bonds or real estate. All assets and liabilities were held at book value. Doing so disguised possible risks arising from how the assets and liabilities were structured.

Objective of the Study

1. To study the concept of asset & liability management.
2. To Study of comparison of asset & liability from balance sheet.
3. To understand the Financial Statement

Scope of the Study

- 1) Geographical Scope:

The Study is related to the Dytech Engineering Product, Ogalewadi.

- 2) Analytical Scope:

Analytical Scope is restricted to the data of analysis using statistical tools such as tables, graphs, ratios etc.

Research Methodology:

Data collection

Research always starts with a question or a problem. Its purpose is to answer questions through the application of the scientific method. It is a systematic and intensive study directed towards a more complete knowledge of the subject studied. Research specifies the information required to address these issues, designs, and the method for collecting information, managing & implementing the data collection process, analyzing the result & communicating the findings and their implications. The main objective of the study is to determine & analyze the financial position of the Dytech Engineering, Wirawade.

During the period of training in dytech engineering information was collected through different ways:

- A. Primary Data
- B. Secondary Data

A) Primary Data

The data is collected through discussion and unstructured interview of management of company. Primary data is that information which is not published but it is very useful data. So the information was collected by discussion held with the executives & finance manager of departments.

B) Secondary Data

Secondary data consist of the information that already exists or someone has collected it for specific purpose secondary data means the information collected on the basis of previous records published and unpublished data. Other information is collected through textbook, other reference book etc... also the secondary data collected from the company records for the study from the company books of accounts & annual reports the company & website of company. Information collected through audited balance sheet of the Dytech Engineering.

1. Annual Report
2. Textbook
3. Company Website

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Comparative Balance Sheet

For the year ended 31st March 2016, 2017, 2018

Liabilities	2016	2017	2018
Capital	332856.65	3558177.93	4266003.12
Secured Loan	3083571.00	3369048.00	2272374.00
Unsecured Loan	2586421.56	2460995.56	2090467.56
Provision	834269.00	494416.49	1131875.63
Sundry Creditors	17529121.20	26792510.66	28835719.01
	27366239.41	40044196.64	38596439.32

Percentage Change in Liabilities

Particulars	Change in amount		Change in %	
	2016	2017	2016	2017
Capital	22321.28	707825.19	6.7606%	19.8929%
Secured Loan	2854477.00	(10966774.00)	9.3579%	(-30.8212%)
Unsecured Loan	(-125426.00)	(-370528.00)	(-4.8494%)	(-15.0560%)
Provisions	(-339852.51)	637459.14	(-4.0736%)	128.9316%
Sundry Creditors	9263389.46	2043208.35	52.84%	7.6260%
	9308909.23	1921290.68	59.93	110.57

Percentage change in Total Liabilities.

Interpretation: -The above table shows that in 2016-17 the percentage of the total liabilities was 59.93% it was decreased to 110.57% increase in the year 2017-18

Comparative Balance Sheet

For the year ended 31st March 2016, 2017, 2018

Assets	2016	2017	2018
Stock	416188.00	1266188.00	766188.00
Sundry Debtors	14189851.20	2010113.17	17218631.72
Cash at Bank	1319390.23	563334.40	2144372.04
Cash in Hand	24424.19	25087.07	69917.42
Investment	195505.00	244425.00	244425.00
Fixed Assets	7163283.11	10056264.14	11144552.14
Loan & Advance	3090432.68	3258809.86	6407043.80
Other Current assets	380342.00	572094.00	36389.20
Deposits	586833.00	586833.00	237490.00
	27366239.41	36675148.64	38596439.32

Percentage change in Assets

Particulars	Change in amount		Change in %	
	2016	2017	2016	2017
Stock	850000	(-500000.00)	204.2346	(-39.4886)
Sundry Debtors	5912263.97	(-2883481.45)	41.6654	(-14.3441)
Cash at bank	(-756045.83)	1581.37.64	-57.3031	269.4736
Cash in Hand	662.88	44830.35	271.4030	178.6990
Investment	48920.00		25.0223	
Fixed Assets	2892981.03	1088288.00	40.3862	10.8219
Loan & Advance	168377.18	3148233.34	5.4483	96.6068
Other Current Assets	191752.00	(-208274.80)	50.4156	(-36.4056)
Deposits	-	(-439343.00)		(-59.5302)
	9308909.23	8688253.58	581.27	405.83

Percentage Change in Total Assets:

Interpretation: -

The above table shows that in 2016-17 the percentage of the total Assets was 581.27% it was increased to 405.83% decreased in the year of 2017-18.

Ratio

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Current Ratio} &= \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}} \\ 2015-16 &= \frac{20007451.30}{17529121.20} \\ &= 1.1413\% \\ 2015-16 &= \frac{26374459.50}{26792510.66} \\ &= 0.9843\% \\ 2015-16 &= \frac{27207462.18}{28835719.01} \\ &= 0.9435\% \end{aligned}$$

Table No. 1 Current Ratio

Year	Percentage %
2015-16	1.1413
2016-17	0.9823
2017-18	0.9435

Graph No.1

Interpretation: -

Current ratio, which represents the capacity of the company to pay its debts maturity within a year. Generally, 2:1 is referred ideal ratio company not as the standard but it changes year by year.

2) Debts equity ratio

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{2) Debts equity ratio} = \frac{\text{Total debts}}{\text{Proprietor's Fund}} \\
 & \text{2015-16} = \frac{38478932.96}{4343506.36} \\
 & \quad = 8.8589 \\
 & \text{2016-17} = \frac{56446369.37}{3820050.85} \\
 & \quad = 14.7763 \\
 & \text{2017-18} = \frac{60893781.21}{4781482.88} \\
 & \quad = 12.7353
 \end{aligned}$$

Table No. 2 Debt Equity Ratio

Year	Debt Equity Ratio Percentage%
2015-16	8.8589
2016-17	14.7763
2017-18	12.7353

Graph No.2

Interpretation:

From the above table and graphs show that, debt equity ratio of every year change. In 2015-16 it is 8.8589% in 2016-2017 it is 14.7763% and last year year i.e. 2017-18 is 12.7353%.

In 2015-2016 the debt equity ratio is the 8.8589% it is lowest, due to total debts are minimum as compare with other financial year. A low debt equity ratio indicates lower risk, since debt holder have fewer claims on the company asset.

3) Liquid Ratio

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{3) Liquid Ratio} = \frac{\text{Liquid Assets}}{\text{Liquid Liabilities}} \\
 & \text{2015-16} = \frac{19591263.30}{17529121.20} \\
 & \quad = 1.1176 \\
 & \text{2016-17} = \frac{25108271.50}{26792510.66} \\
 & \quad = 0.9371 \\
 & \text{2017-18} = \frac{26441274.18}{28835719.01} \\
 & \quad = 0.9169
 \end{aligned}$$

Table No. 3 Liquid Ratio

Year	Liquid Ratio Percentage%
2015-16	1.1176
2016-17	0.9371
2017-18	0.9169

Interpretation:-

The above table shows that the quick ratio in the year 2015-16 was 11.8% & in the year of 2016-17 and 2017-18 was decreased 0.93% & 0.91 %.

4) Proprietors Fund Ratio

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{4) Proprietors Fund Ratio} = \frac{\text{Proprietor's Fund}}{\text{Total Assets}} \\
 & \text{2015-16} = \frac{4343506.36}{27366239.41} \\
 & \quad = 0.1587 \\
 & \text{2016-17} = \frac{3820050.85}{36675148.64} \\
 & \quad = 0.1041 \\
 & \text{2017-18} = \frac{4781482.88}{28596439.32} \\
 & \quad = 0.1238
 \end{aligned}$$

Table No. 4 Proprietors Fund Ratio

Year	Proprietors Fund Ratio Percentage%
2015-16	0.1587
2016-17	0.1041
2017-18	0.1238

Interpretation:-

From the above table it is found that the trend of the proprietor's funds ratio is fluctuation. It was decreased in 2016-17 but as it increases in 2015-16.

5) Fixed asset Ratio

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{5) Fixed Asset Ratio} &= \frac{\text{Fixed Assets}}{\text{Long Term Fund}} \\
 \\
 \text{2015-16} &= \frac{7163283.11}{2291301.00} \\
 &= 3.1262 \\
 \text{2016-17} &= \frac{10056264.14}{3007460.00} \\
 &= 3.3437 \\
 \text{2017-18} &= \frac{11144552.14}{2272374.00} \\
 &= 4.9043
 \end{aligned}$$

Table No. 6 Fixed Asset Ratio

Year	Fixed asset Ratio Percentage%
2015-16	3.1262
2016-17	3.3437
2017-18	4.9043

Interpretation:-

The above table shows that ratio of fixed assets ratio is increasing trend. The fixed asset ratio is calculated in the 3.12 in 2014, and 3.34 in 2017, 4.90 in 2018. Here we can see company three year charts and graphs which shows the fixed assets ratio. The ratio 2017-2018 is higher than other ratio.

Table No. 8 Current Liability

Year	Fixed asset Ratio Percentage %
2015-16	18363390.2
2016-17	27286927.15
2017-18	29967594.24

Interpretation:-

Form the above table and graphs show that, current liabilities are decrease in 2015-16 Current liability is aliquidity position of an organization current liability is increase in 2017-18.

Current Assets = Stock + Sundry Debtors + Cash at Bank + Cash in Hand + Investment

$$2015-2016 = 416188 + 14189851.20 + 1319380.23 + 195505.00$$

$$= 16145348.62$$

$$2016-17 = 1266188 + 20102113.17 + 563334.40 + 25087.07 + 244425$$

$$= 22201447.64$$

$$2017-18 = 766188 + 17218631.72 + 2144372.04 + 69917.42 + 244425$$

$$= 20443534.18$$

Table No. 7 Current Assets

Year	Current Assets
2015-16	16145348.62
2016-17	22201147.64
2017-18	20443534.18

Interpretation

The above graph shows that, current asset is decrease in 2015-16 and 2017-18 Current asset should improve actual condition of company the current asset is increased in 2016-2017.

Findings

1. The current ratio is mostly used ratio & proportion is 2:1 is considered to satisfactory but that ratio is not satisfied.
2. The debt equity ratio is low in 2015-16 comparing to the years 2016-17 & 2017-18 is increased.
3. The liquid ratio is high in the 2015-16 compare to the years 2016-17 & 2017-18.
4. The fixed assets ratio in increased in 2017-18 that is affecting company's total assets.
5. The current liabilities are to be increased year by year & that is not good for the company.
6. The current assets are high in 2016-17 is comparing to the 2015-16 and 2017-18 .
7. The comparative balance sheet is showing the assets and liabilities and that are affecting company's profitability.

Conclusion

The researcher concludes from the detailed study “assets and liabilities management” with respect to Dytech Engineering that the financial position of the company is satisfactory. The company give to that it has a good prospective future. From this project I could get an overall view of the company. The study of assets and liability management shows that the fluctuation trends in organization & at the same time company passes some weak points.

References:

1. Raghavan, R.S (2005) Risk Management – overview in S.B.Verma(2ndedition). Risk Management, Deep and Deep publication private ltd, New Delhi.
2. Ravi Kumar (2005), Asset and Liability Management(2ndedition), Vision Books.
3. Shashi K Gupta, R.K.Sharma and Anuj Gupta (2014), Management Accounting (2ndEdition), Kalyani Publication
4. Mr. Chetan Shetty and Ms. Pooja Patel (2016) ‘An analysis on Asset Liability Management’, International Journal of Research in IT and Management (IJRIM), Vol.6, Issue 10, Oct, pages 92-98. Source: <https://www.eurosiapub.org>
5. Dr. K. Prince Paul Antony (2018) ‘A study on ALM in Indian Bank’, International Journal of Business Administration and Management, Vol.8, pages: 1-9. Source: <https://www.ripublication.com>